

The concept of a channeling system for satellite mobile communication for media delivery with increased efficiency

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Abstract – European society aims to facilitate the digitalization of European society across all vertical sectors. Digitalization is accelerating through the development and implementation of modern 5G networks everywhere. In these conditions satellite subsystem become an integral part of current version of 5G networks, which will be used for the different use cases. One of them is high-resolution video broadcasting using satellite channels. This paper analysis exactly this use case and proposes the new architecture of channeling system for satellite mobile communication for media delivery with increased efficiency. To optimize this system also a mathematical model was proposed.

Keywords – 5G, satellite communication, efficiency, channeling, media delivery, broadcasting.

I. INTRODUCTION

The disruptions around the world from Covid-19 have put a great deal of pressure on companies to adapt to abrupt changes just to survive. A majority (95%) of global leaders surveyed said that digital transformation has taken on more importance in the last 12 months, likely because of the pandemic. In these conditions DIGITALEUROPE aims to facilitate the digitalization of European society across all vertical sectors [1]. Digital technologies increase productivity, improve energy efficiency and uncover data-based business models. Strategies and policies are discussed in order to realize Society 5.0 [2], extend healthy life expectancy and improve the quality of life.

Digitalization is accelerating through the development and implementation of new information and communication technologies (ICT) solutions in general and the launch of modern 5G networks everywhere.

The telecoms industry is undergoing a major transformation towards 5G and 6G networks in order to fulfill the needs of existing and emerging use cases (Automotive, Smart Grids, UAVs, PPDR, etc.). So the vision of 5G/6G wireless networks lies in providing very high data rates and higher coverage through dense base station deployment with increased capacity, significantly better Quality of Experience (QoE), and extremely low latency. To provide the necessary services envisioned by 5G/6G, novel networking, service deployment, storage and processing technologies will be required. These technologies should bring new challenges for the 5G technologies and its functionality.

5G and beyond will connect critical infrastructure that will require more reliable connections and alternatives for data transferring, like satellite communication channels. This paper focuses on the usage of satellite channels for video delivery with ultra-high resolution.

II. BACKGROUND WORK

It is now become obvious that satellite subsystem become an integral part of current version of 5G networks [3]. Satellite communications have recently entered a period of renewed interest motivated by technological advances and nurtured through private investment and ventures. The survey [4] captured the state of the art in SatComs, while highlighting the most promising open research topics [5]. Analyzed the the directions of development and implementation problems of 5G communication systems, including satellite part.

More detailed study of the satellite channels characteristics, its modeling, influence of different external parameters was done in [6 – 8]. But most of these research papers were devoted to the physical layer of data transmission.

Regarding the potential usage of satellite channel for data delivery for moving objects, then research on the broadcast channel parameters was done in [9].

But all of analyzed above research papers did not deal with the channels organization for high-speed moving objects. Present research will be directly devoted to the development of new and updates of existing schemes for channeling system for satellite mobile communication for media delivery, which can be used in the future 5G Advanced and 6G networks.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

However, none of the standards contains proposals for the structure of channel-forming equipment, architecture and algorithms for managing information signals in a network with the following parameters:

- network capacity up to 2000 mobile subscribers;
- simultaneous servicing of each mobile subscriber at a speed of 12MB / sec;

- the speed of movement of subscribers from 0 km / h to 1200 km / h (the last figure reflects the speed of movement of drones by 10 km in 30 seconds);
- network reliability;
- the cost of the equipment included in the network.

That's why it is necessary to develop novel architecture for satellite mobile communications in accordance with listed above requirements.

IV. CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MAIN COMMUNICATION CONTROL CENTERS (CCC)

For the convenience of presenting access networks of different types, we will group them in three spatial zones, which include: the Internet core, communication control centers with their own access networks in the form of satellite channels, terrestrial fiber optic, radio relay wireless and other communication lines (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. Proposed concept

Below is a list, purpose and composition of equipment for communication control centers.

CCC 1 – connected by satellite radio channels with receiving-transmitting devices of intermediate base stations by two-way communication in railway express trains. This center collects all information from various sources to compile a preliminary menu of media services for express subscribers and to carry out

simultaneous transmission of media programs for a dozen railways, express trains.

CCC 2 – connected by satellite radio channels with two-way receiving-transmitting devices in the head car to provide subscribers with media services in its express train.

CCC 3 – through satellite channels, carries out simultaneous synchronous transmission of media programs for two thousand automobile subscribers moving in random directions of movement within the

coverage of the territory with one beam of the spacecraft antenna in geostationary orbit.

CCC 4 – via satellite channels it transmits command signals during attacks and defense to combat units of drones that fly to combat positions at a speed of about 600-1200 km / h.

V. TRANSMISSION CHANNEL CHARACTERISTICS

It is known that an analog television (TV) signal with duration of 1 second has a spectrum with an upper frequency equal to 6 MHz, then for sampling its frequency axis it is enough to take samples of its level in $13.5 \cdot 100000$ samples. Since there are 256 levels in the level scale, and a three-digit digit can be encoded in

8 bits, a digitized analog TV signal with a duration of 1 second, with a quality standard of 4: 2: 2, can be transmitted without distortion at a transmission rate of 216 Mb / s. To estimate the needed capacity of satellite channels its bandwidth has to be calculated.

The required bandwidth of operating frequencies in the satellite radio channel can be calculated using the formula below [10]:

$$\Delta f_{ir} = \frac{(13,5 \cdot 10^6 + 6,75 \cdot 10^6 \cdot 2) \cdot 8 [Hz]}{K_{MPEG}(50;100) \cdot FEC(5/6;1/2;3/4) \cdot K_M(1;2;3;4;5;6)}$$

Table 1 shows the results of calculating the required bandwidth for subcarriers for different initial parameters for two band 12 and 18 GHz accordingly.

TABLE 1
REQUIRED BANDWIDTH FOR SUBCARRIERS FOR DIFFERENT INITIAL PARAMETERS

1	Transponder parameters	$f_{s1} = 12 \text{ HHZ}; P_{ir}^{transp} = 20 \text{ W}; \Delta f_{transp} = 100 \text{ MHz}.$											
2	Signal parameters	$\Delta f_{TV} = 216 \cdot 10^6 / FEC \cdot K_M \cdot K_{MPEG} [MHz].$											
3	MPEG	$K_{MPEG2}=50$						$K_{MPEG4}=100$					
4	$K_M=$	1	2	3	4	5	6	1	2	3	4	5	6
5	FEC=1/2	8,64	4,32	2,88	2,16	1,73	1,64	4,32	2,16	1,44	1,08	0,86	0,72
6	FEC=5/6	5,18	2,59	1,73	1,295	1,036	0,86	2,59	1,29	0,86	0,647	0,52	0,43
7	FEC=3/4	5,76	2,88	1,92	1,44	1,152	0,96	2,88	1,44	0,96	0,72	0,58	0,48
8	Transponder parameters	$f_{s2} = 18 \text{ HHZ}; P_{ir}^{transp} = 40 \text{ W}; \Delta f_{transp} = 200 \text{ MHz}.$											
9	Signal parameters	$\Delta f_{TV} = 216 \cdot 10^6 / FEC \cdot K_M \cdot K_{MPEG} [MHz].$											
10	MPEG	$K_{MPEG2}=50$						$K_{MPEG4}=100$					
11	$K_M=$	1	2	3	4	5	6	1	2	3	4	5	6
12	FEC=1/2	8,64	4,32	2,88	2,16	1,73	1,64	4,32	2,16	1,44	1,08	0,86	0,72
13	FEC=5/6	5,18	2,59	1,73	1,295	1,036	0,86	2,59	1,29	0,86	0,647	0,52	0,43
14	FEC=3/4	5,76	2,88	1,92	1,44	1,152	0,96	2,88	1,44	0,96	0,72	0,58	0,48

In Table 1: f_{s1} – operating frequencies range; P_{ir}^{transp} – transponder’s transmitter power; Δf_{transp} – transponder bandwidth; Δf_{TV} – one TV-program bandwidth; K_{MPEG2} – compression ratio with the MPEG2 program; K_M – modulation factor; FEC – redundancy factor at noiseless coding; K_{MPEG4} – compression ratio with the MPEG4 program.

VI. OPTIMIZED MULTI-BUTTED TASK METHOD

Algorithms and the Aggregative Model and the given initial data allows to generate hundreds of thousands of variants of the satellite communication system.

Only by calculating one parameter, by going through parameters, 432 variants can be organized. With the

same variety of two more parameters y_2^n and y_3^n , the total number of variants of system construction can reach hundreds of thousands of combinations.

Based on the developed by authors generalized method of solution of the synthesis problem for systems, which were developing on the technical task, new construction of objective function is proposed for the first time for telecommunication systems [10]:

$$\Phi = \prod_{i=3}^3 R_i \cdot y_i^n = (R_1 \cdot y_1^n) \cdot (R_2 \cdot y_2^n) \cdot (R_3 \cdot y_3^n),$$

where: y_i^n – normalized optimization parameters, R_i - Boolean function, equal to “1” if the value meets the technical requirements, or “0” if not satisfied.

The Boolean function was introduced by the authors into the design of the objective function to establish the principle: “if the parameter is indicated in the technical

task, it must necessarily be fulfilled". This principle corresponds to the requirements of experimental-construction works, when the answer to compliance. The above optimization parameters allow us to take into account the consumer requirements for building a satellite broadcasting system for TV programs.

1. The new design of the objective function makes it possible to significantly reduce the range of permissible values by using the Boolean function.

2. The objective function takes into account the technical requirements for building a satellite network and reduces to a single value for building one system. Due to this, TV-program broadcasting systems can be compared with each other and we draw a conclusion which one is preferable

3. The method for the synthesis of parameters in the structure of the satellite system and the distribution of TV channels gives the possibility to select the effective options for the distribution of signals for any region. Mathematical modeling confirms the effectiveness of the given method.

The technical requirements can only be "yes" or "no". The Boolean function introduced this categoricity into the construction of the objective function.

Multiplication of objective function's multipliers makes it more sensitive for changes. Thus, for example, objective function, which consists of summands, practically does not react if any summand is set to zero, because in this case the total sum practically will not change.

The analytical expression for the generalized FML criterion, which was called the integral preference criterion (IPC) has the following form:

Studies have shown that the objective function F meets all the requirements and has a high solving power. F allows dividing the entire set of compared systems into two subsets. One of them is a set of systems that do not satisfy at least one requirement of TDS ($\Phi = 0$). The second subset ($0 < \Phi \leq 1$) allows you

to rank systems by the degree of satisfaction of the TDS requirements. The integral preference criterion allows not only to take into account all existing forms of TDS requirements, but also to distinguish variants that have large reserves in terms of parameters relative to the requirements in TDS, that ensures greater parametric reliability of the system being developed.

From the table it follows that for the 18 GHz band the required number of programs can provide from two till eight or more transponders. The power level of the signal emitted by the transponder antenna for the transmission of one TV program is determined after performing three calculations.

First, let us determine the frequency band occupied by one TV program at different values of the redundancy factor with error-correcting coding (FEC), with different compression programs (MPEG), with different types of modulation ($K_m = 1, 2, 4, 6$) Additional basic data for solving the problem of the synthesis based on the block diagram of aggregate model of the system of distribution network TV-programs

Given initial data allows to generate hundreds of thousands of variants of the satellite of combinations.

VII. THE STRUCTURAL SCHEMA OF ES AGGREGATIVE MODEL

The fig. 2 shows graphical representation an aggregate mathematical model of the system of a downlink broadband satellite radio channel, consisting of an AS transponder, a route between A1 and A2, and an earth station (ES).

A graphical representation of the aggregate model (Fig. 2) describes: the structure of the spacecraft, the parameters of the transponder, the connecting microwave path and its dividers, adders, duplexers, etc., antenna parameters.

Fig 2. The Structural Schema Aggregative model of ES

IX. CONCLUSION

Development of telecommunication systems (fixed and mobile) to the requirements of 5G is conceptually possible to designate the following parameters:

1. The main technical solutions for transmission and reception signal processing must be based on the principle of data centrism technology OFDM, OTFDM, energy saving technology and others.

2. Schematics and design solutions should be developed in the literal execution of the rows in the same type of element base.

3. Free access signal to any subscriber must be provided without the procedure of handover.

4. Speed of movement subscribers in mobile telecommunication to 500 km/h and for dual use of 3000 km/hour.

5. High speed data transmission on the forward link to each subscriber of 10 Mbits/sec to 100 Mbits/sec.

6. Estimated range of frequencies up to 300 GHz.

7. Quality Indicators $SNR \geq 20 \text{ dB}$; $P_{g.o.o.} \leq 10^{-5} - 10^{-6}$.

8. Network displacement from units N to several thousands ($N \times 1000$) subscribers. The integral part of such 5G mobile communication system is the satellite segment, which by the optimization of mentioned above parameters allow taking into account the consumer requirements for the construction of a TV programs satellite broadcasting system. For this purpose new architecture of channeling system for satellite mobile

communication for media delivery with increased efficiency was developed.

For this new architecture also was applied the optimization technique. The new design of the objective function makes it possible to reduce significantly the range of permissible values by using the Boolean function. The objective function takes into account the technical requirements for building a satellite network and reduces to a single value for the construction of a system.

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